

Reattachment of Complicated Crown Fracture: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Coronal fractures of the anterior teeth are a common form of dental trauma. If the original tooth fragment is retained following fracture, reattachment of the fractured fragment to the remaining tooth can provide better and long lasting esthetics, improved function, a positive psychological response, and is a faster and less complicated procedure. This paper reports a case of coronal tooth fracture that was successfully treated using adhesive reattachment of fractured fragment and post placement.

INTRODUCTION

Complicated crown fractures are one of the most common types of fractures involving anterior teeth, most commonly affecting the maxillary incisors, forming 96% of all crown fractures.¹ Etiological factors of crown-root fractures of permanent dentition are falls, sports injuries, car accidents, and foreign body striking the teeth.² Such a tooth requires immediate clinical attention. The ultimate goal of any dental emergency treatment is to re-establish normal tooth position and function. Divakar and Nayak (2007) reported that crown fractures have been documented to account for up to 92% of all traumatic injuries to the permanent dentition. Numerous techniques to restore fractured crowns have emerged in recent years. Conventionally, composite restorations and post-and-core supported prostheses are the most commonly used modalities. The treatment plan may vary when the fractured fragment is available and intact.

Reattachment of the fractured fragment using the adhesive technique can be the most immediate and conservative treatment option concerning esthetics if the fractured portion is

intact and the margins are preserved as it involves minimal intervention and biological restoration of the natural tooth. The tooth reattachment technique can restore a patient's esthetics, form, contour, alignment, translucence, surface texture, and position of the tooth within a short span of time. Many options are there for the reattachment of the fractured tooth fragment. In case of complicated crown-root fractures where the fractured segments are closely approximating, root canal treatment followed by reattachment of the fractured segment with fiber post reinforcement is a suitable option. Tooth colored fiber posts have several advantages such as esthetics, bonding to the tooth structure, and a similar modulus of elasticity as that of dentin. Also, it provides a monoblock effect thereby increasing the retention of the complex by enhancing the fitness of the post for the prepared root canal.³

In this case report, the management of a complicated crown fracture involving a central and lateral incisor by reattachment using fiber post, is described.

CASE REPORT

A 24-year-old female patient reported to the Department of Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics with chief complaint of detached fragment in upper left front region of jaw due to road traffic accident. Patient had already visited a private dental clinic for treatment immediately following a road traffic accident. The dentist had placed composite over the fracture line buccally & palatally with 21 & 22. (Fig. 1,2)

Fig 1: Pre operative clinical photograph (Labial & palatal view)

Clinical examination revealed a class III fracture in 21 & 22 with the fracture line running obliquely from the gingival third of the tooth on the labial aspect to palatal side subgingivally. In addition, incisal edge was fractured with 21 & 22. However, these fragments were lost. A radiograph indicated the horizontal fracture lines, radiopaque restorative material in the coronal part of 21/ 22, complete root formation and a closed apex with no periapical radiolucency and did not show any other fracture or injury on the adjacent teeth. Periodontal ligament space was intact and no root fracture was seen in relation to 21 and 22. (fig 2)

Fig 2: Pre- operative radiograph

Medical history was non-contributory. After discussing various treatment options with the patient, reattachment of the coronal fragment with the remaining tooth structure, followed by composite restoration of fractures incisal edge, was planned. The patient's informed consent was obtained before initiation of the treatment. Single visit root canal treatment was started with 21 & 22. Composite was removed & fracture line was clearly visible (Fig. 3). Local anesthesia was administered (1.0 cc of lidocaine 2% with 1:80,000 epinephrine) and the coronal segments were removed with minimal force, recovered and stored in normal saline to prevent discoloration and dehydration (Fig. 4 & 5).

Fig 3: Fracture line visible

Fig 4: Fractured fragment

It was decided to use a fiber post for reattaching the fractured fragment with 21 & 22. Access opening was done with 21 & 22. After gaining an adequate access, canal orifice was negotiated, initial inspection of the root canal was done with no.10 K-file, and the patency of root canal was established. The working length was estimated using an electronic apex locator and confirmed with radiograph (fig 6).

Fig 5: Clinical photograph after fractured fragment removal

Fig 6: Working length determination

Cleaning & shaping was done using Neo Endo rotary file up to 6% taper 30 size of the instrument. Copious irrigation was done with 5.2% sodium hypochlorite, & 17% EDTA/saline were used as final irrigant. After taking master cone radiograph obturation was done by sectional obturation method with 21 & 22 along with AH Plus sealer. (Fig 7). Post space was prepared using Peeso reamers of sizes 1, 2, and 3. A fiber reinforced post of size 2 was selected for both teeth and the length of the post was adjusted so that 2 mm was extending coronally to the fractured segment. The prepared post space was conditioned and adhesive application was done on fiber post, post space, and tooth fragments with 21 & 22 (Fig. 8 & 9).

Fig 7: Master cone radiograph space

Fig 8: Sectional gutta percha & Post space

Space was also prepared in the pulp chamber of both the fractured crown fragment for receiving the coronal portion of the post. For the reattachment of the fragments, a dual cure resin cement (Multilink Automix, Ivoclar) was used. This dual cure resin cement has a solid bond, complete curing, and limited microleakage. After fixation of fractured fragment with 21 & 22, absence of any mobility was confirmed (Fig 10). Composite restoration was done for fractured crown structure with 21 & 22. (Fig. 11 & 12).

Fig 9: Fiber post luted with 21 and 22

Fig 10: Attachment of fracture fragment

Fig 11: Composite restoration with 21 & 22

Fig 12: Post Operative radiograph

DISCUSSION

Restoring structural integrity, function, and esthetics are the most important factors when it comes to the management of traumatized anterior teeth. First described by Chosack and Eidelman, if the fractured fragment is available intact at the right time, reattachment has

to be the most desired treatment.⁴ As it offers good esthetics, an exact recreation of contacts and contour, and a very cost-effective treatment alternative rather than restoring it prosthetically.

It also aids in the social and psychological well-being of a patient. In addition, tooth fragment reattachment allows restoration of the tooth with minimal sacrifice of the remaining tooth structure. Many case reports and researches in the literature suggest that reattachment of a fractured tooth fragment is a viable approach for the treatment of coronal fracture of anterior teeth when the fractured segment is available.⁵ The success of the reattachment depends on several factors: hydration of the fractured segment while outside the oral cavity is one of them.⁶ This is necessary to maintain the original esthetic appearance of the tooth and also ensures adequate bond strength. If the extraoral time of the fractured fragment increases, dehydration of the fragment can occur. Therefore, to prevent this, it is recommended that the fragment be kept in a medium such as physiologic saline, and the fragments were kept in artificial saliva to prevent dehydration. When there is a substantial associated periodontal injury and/ or invasion of the biological width, the restorative management of the coronal fracture should also consider the rehabilitation of those associated tissues.⁷

Reinforcement of the reattached fragments using posts has been widely reported in the literature. Although many techniques with various materials have been suggested, resin based restorative materials with fiber post may be considered the best option because of several advantages such as a suitable elastic modulus, esthetics, good bonding between post and cement, lower chairside time, and minimal tissue removal. In addition to the preparation of the post space, bigger access was created in the coronal separated segment as leeway for the excess cement to flow out without build-up of any hydrostatic pressure.⁵

In the present case, the management was complicated because of fracture & loss incisal edge fragments, in addition to the crown fracture. Hence, reattachment of the fractured fragments was done using the fiber post & the incisal edges were restored by composite restoration.

Reattached teeth are subjected to more stress and strain compared to the normal tooth. They are prone to re-fracture, so the reattached fragments have to be well bonded to withstand different types of forces. Modern composite materials with their advanced physical and esthetic properties can be used to create good quality esthetic restorations.⁸

CONCLUSION

Reattachment of fractured fragments is a conservative approach in restoring fractured anterior teeth in a simple, economical, effective manner to restore the esthetic form and function of teeth.

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